

PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE HISTORY OF SOCIO-POLITICAL REFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article expressed views on some threats characteristic of the transition period in Uzbekistan, the fight against religious and political extremism carried out to seize power, analyzed the essence of political reforms carried out on the basis of the ideas of national ideology, capable of countering it. Based on the initial experience of reforming the country, the basic principles of further development of society have been developed. They coped with the task of strengthening stability and restoring society. The article is devoted to the analysis of the history of these processes and their peculiarities.

Keywords: independence, states, political reform, democracy, stability, transition, civil society

Introduction

Today Uzbekistan is in the process of establishing a free society among developing countries. Over the past years, a number of concepts covering the processes of liberalization and modernization of society's life have been put into practice. Systematic work was carried out to ensure human rights, strengthen the accountability and openness of state bodies, and increase the role of civil society institutions, mass media, and the political activity of citizens and public associations.

Some results were achieved on the basis of measures taken to reform the national economy, liberalize foreign trade, tax and financial policy, support entrepreneurship

and guarantee the inviolability of private property, organize processing of agricultural products, and ensure rapid development of regions.

Enhancing the social protection of citizens and reducing poverty has been defined as a priority of the state policy, providing the population with new jobs and a guaranteed source of income, qualified medical and educational services, and decent living conditions has been raised to a new level in terms of quality

As a result of the last five-year reforms, the necessary political-legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational foundations for the establishment of New Uzbekistan were created in our country.

Reforms aimed at further increasing the well-being of our people, transforming economic sectors and intensively developing entrepreneurship, unconditionally ensuring human rights and interests, and forming an active civil society, are being carried out based on a thorough analysis of the progress of our country. The development strategy of new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 has been accepted, and within its framework consistent reforms are being continued based on the following directions [1].

1. Establishing a people-friendly state by increasing human dignity and further developing a free civil society;
2. Making the principles of justice and the rule of law the most basic and necessary condition for development in our country;
3. Rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates;
4. Fair social policy, development of human capital;
5. Ensuring spiritual development and bringing the industry to a new level;
6. Approaching universal problems based on national interests;
7. To strengthen the security and defense potential of our country, to conduct an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy.

Our goal in this article is to analyze the complexities of the transitional period and its specific aspects in the first years of independence in Uzbekistan.

2. Some threats and challenges of the transition period

The socio-economic difficulties of the transition period are a breeding ground for the purposeful incitement of social confrontations, the disintegration of society, the creation of conditions in which it is easy to "distort" the truth, to give out private interests for the interests of society and the nation, to offer people radical ideas and extremist ways to implement them.

During the transition period of society from one social system to another, there will always be ambitious individuals and their like-minded people who, at their own choice, have found themselves outside the legitimate boundaries of the political process. They do not care what the country needs, the nation. They are important in their own importance and power, for which they are able to take on various arguments, even divergent from their own ideas about the truth. Here, as a rule, there are psychological factors of those who during the period of apparent uncertainty did not have time to take "their own". The curb of the political relations on which such politicians find themselves exacerbates their self-esteem even more, and they, infringed by a sense of political lack of demand and having once felt a taste for power, which they thought were just a stone's throw away - begin to pass into the illegal plane of activity. In this period, it is important to warn all that can be at the mercy of the unconstitutional forces. Alternative: variants of the Tajik events of 1992-1994.

The society should have known that such people not only use for their own ends the difficulties of the transition period, but they also do everything to create them artificially, and if it does not turn out then with the help of ideological methods of struggle (through propaganda in the mass media, leaflets, through direct contact with the audience, through missionary activities, etc.) create the appearance of problems, give out wishful thinking.

Such parties as "Erk", "Birlik", etc. at one time they spoke and would oppose any legitimate political power, where there was no place for their representatives. In the period of aggravation of the crisis in the disintegrating USSR in mid-1991, the most

characteristic position of political parties was radicalism, intransigence and a claim to the leading role in society. This radicalism did not weaken even after gaining independence.

All the efforts of the Government of Uzbekistan were directed to the weakening of the radicalism and the conflict nature of a number of political neoplasms, realizing that the path of confrontation is fraught with destabilization of the socio-political situation in the country. The positive solution of the main issues of ensuring national sovereignty, the process of democratization, accompanied by the dismantling of totalitarian power structures, only increased the non-constructiveness of oppositional forces against the official authority. Even then it became obvious that a number of parties (or rather their leaders) took the path that can be expressed in the thesis: "Power at any cost, under any ideology."

It is noteworthy that when the "critical" material ends, there is no corresponding texture, the "non-constructive" opposition strives to emphasize the radicalization of its claims and claims, or even changes its ideological credo. So, many "democrats" suddenly became "warriors of Allah", pseudo-democratic rhetoric was replaced by a theological one. In general, the strategy of the "first" radical opponents of the current government was aimed at using objectively existing contradictions for their own purposes, building on the third forces, which in turn had their own views on Uzbekistan, providing ideological and material assistance to new allies. This fact also affected the strategy of political reform. There arose a vital need for the formation of an ideological system capable not only of opposing religious and political extremism, but also fulfilling the function of the concept of political reforms.

Such a system began to be formed on the basis of ideas of national independence. The task was to formulate its content in such a way that it fully reflected the national interests, its needs, values, principles and norms.

The political essence of this ideology can be expressed in the disclosure of the three principles of political reform: democracy, independence and stability. It was

necessary to show that these principles are important only when they are correctly understood and correctly used. For example, hypertrophied, inadequate understanding of "democracy" can be tied down by the state apparatus (especially in the sphere of law enforcement). "Stability" can be transformed into stagnation, and "independence" in isolationism. Therefore, it was important to disclose these principles as contributing to the achievement of the main goal, but not the very goal, or a system of sub-goals.

3. Principles of reforms

When speaking about the principles, implemented in Uzbekistan, reforms, it is necessary to note, first of all, a commitment to the ideas of independence, human rights. Responsibility to present and future generations, reliance on the historical experience of development of Uzbek statehood, fidelity to the ideals of democracy and social justice, the priority of the norms of international law.

Political power belongs to the people, the interests and will of which the state expresses and serves. State bodies and officials are unconditionally responsible to the society and citizens. The development of this principle is the most important condition for the development of civil society. The people, according to the Constitution, being the only source of state power, express it only through the "Oliy Majlis" and the President of the Republic (which they are elected). The most important issues of public and state life are brought to the discussion of the people, put to a general vote (referendum). At the same time, no part of the society, political party, public association, movement or individual can speak on behalf of the people of Uzbekistan.

The principles of political development rely on the system of separation of powers, the diversity of political instruments, ideologies and opinions, the prohibition of ideological monopoly. Democracy is based on universal principles, according to which the highest value is a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights. The state builds its activities on the principles of social justice and legality in the interests of human and social welfare, ensures observance of the rights and legitimate interests of public associations, creates equal legal opportunities for

them to participate in public life.

It is also necessary to note here that we are talking about the fundamental and system-forming principles that determine not only the norms of political relations, but also political ethics, have the significance of the constitutional imperative in legislation, can serve as the basis for law enforcement activities, etc. For example, justice, as a principle, is understood as a legal and moral requirement. In accordance with this principle, the norms of behavior of participants in the political process are determined. This principle prescribes what actions a person, a party, a society, as a whole must perform, without violating the rights of others, so that anyone's right is not infringed. In this sense, justice is a category of law that must meet the requirements of the rule of law and civil society; otherwise the equity criteria may shift to conflicting positions. It is important to correctly understand the criteria of justice, which, for example, in the interpretation of the ideologists of "Wahhabism" alone, in the modern democratic understanding, others. It is the democratic understanding of justice that is reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and in the ideology of political reforms. The above ideas and principles have universal significance and will not lose their relevance after the completion of the main transformations of the political system.

The understanding of the first experience, ways and methods of reforms led the country's leadership to the need to formulate fundamental principles, which were later called "five principles" or "Uzbek model of reforming." First of all, this is the above-mentioned principle of step-by-step reforms.

Further, the most important task of building a new statehood was the solution of economic problems, the ideologies of the economy, and its transfer to market lines. Hence the principle: the priority of the economy over politics. This principle had universal significance and determined the character and direction of all subsequent transformations. In addition to the fact that the concentration of social forces on the reform of the economic system and strong social policy removed social tension and

pushed the ground out of the destabilizing factors, the economy's priority over politics was also indicated by the rejection of administrative and command methods of economic management and approved the course for the formation of such social relations, which are based on a market economy. This circumstance also affected the nature of the construction of a new system of public administration, which was originally carried out in accordance with the requirements of market relations. In particular, the totalitarian structures of political and economic governance were eliminated; principles, forms and methods of government were revised. The planning and administrative functions have been withdrawn from the department and given to the state administration as the coordinator and regulator of economic policy.

In this complex transition period, only the state possessed all the socio-political, legal, organizational and economic resources of Uzbek society, including personnel, finance, property, the real power of state power, natural wealth, political and legal institutions, and in part the authority and influence that by inheritance from the old historical era, from here the principle the state-reformer.

The principle that the state assumes responsibility for carrying out reforms, again had also great psychological significance. On the one hand, it was necessary to change the hypertrophied understanding of the role of the state in the life of society and the individual, on the other, it was necessary to dispose of a certain syndrome that is characterized by the unconditional loyalty of the majority of people in relation to the state system. Part of it was due to innate feelings of state dependence, which the person experienced in the conditions of totalitarian guardianship and regulation. In the state, people saw real power, and it would be an inexcusable mistake to weaken the state administration in the very conditions when a consistent, professional and authoritative government was able to ensure the selection and implementation of development strategy and policy, to take the economy out of crisis and consolidate society. It was the renewed system of public administration that could solve the tasks of political and economic reform, become a means of public consent, and conduct a competent

personnel policy, reliable information monitoring, coordination and public legal regulation.

For this purpose, the new system of public administration had to acquire certain properties, combining flexibility, efficiency, professionalism, openness, etc. The principle of "reforming state" could not only fulfill the tasks of the subject of reforms, but also change the ideas about the state, its essence in the conditions of democracy, in the conditions of building legal statehood.

The scrapping of the administrative command system was based on the need to build a new system of state relations. As a constitutional basis, the theory of the rule of law was adopted. According to this theory, the purpose of the state system should be servicing the needs of civil society, ensuring the rule of law and laws, providing guarantees of administrative interference in the self-regulating processes of society, protecting the interests of producers and socially unprotected layers of the public in a generally accessible due process of law, e. The main thing: it was necessary to ensure the supremacy of the Constitution and the legislation based on it, where all the internationally recognized attributes of guarantees for the protection and protection of human rights and freedoms should have been reflected. Hence the following principle: the rule of law.

The supremacy of law is the way to build a rule-of-law state. In a law-based state, conditions are seen that guarantee the legal equality of all citizens before the law, the rule of law, the protection of the interests of society and the security of the population. "The rule of law is inconceivable without the triumph of law and order, the priority of individual rights and freedoms, firm discipline, internal self-organization and responsibility, respect for laws and traditions" [2]. Through the rule of law, which "contributes to the self-development of a person, the realization of the interests of the individual, to the maximum functioning of her rights and freedoms", the definition of civil society was seen.

The tasks of ensuring the priority of legality also stem from the need to overcome

the negative legacy of totalitarianism, which is expressed: in the absence of proper political and legal institutions; laws and mechanisms for their implementation; in the old thinking, where human rights were not allocated as a priority value and were not included in the system of ensuring national interests as a basic criterion; in the double standards of the ideological philosophy of social relations; in the absence of a state approach to the problems of ensuring human rights, etc.

The fifth principle was announced - a strong social policy, ensuring social protection of the population.

The deterioration of the macroeconomic situation in the initial period of independence limited the possibilities of finding domestic resources for social purposes, whereas the need for them increased due to the implementation of fundamental reforms in the economy and in public life in general. Circumstances required not only finding additional funds, but also changing the structure of their distribution to the social sector because of the need to increase the costs of such social protection measures as income support in connection with inflation, unemployment, etc.

In accordance with this principle in 1991-1994. Support was provided for the population's income in connection with the liberalization of prices and the growth of inflation (in 1994, compared to 1991, 1129 times). The consumer market was being protected, traditionally being in great dependence on imports; thirdly, support for low-income groups of the population. The main principle that was adhered to at this stage was the proactive social protection of the broad strata of the population, which ensures the control of the situation. The main task is to prevent a sharp decline in the standard of living of the population. In solving this problem, the arsenal of methods and methods of direct state regulation was widely used: cash payments, various types of benefits, subsidies for covering the difference in prices for consumer goods and services, a ticket system for the distribution of the most important types of food and non-food products.

Further, a gradual transition from a system of universal social protection to a

system of reliable social guarantees and social support for the most vulnerable segments of the population was carried out. The main principle on which this system is built is the steady observance of the dominant of justice and a decisive departure from the equalizing system of social assistance; a differentiated approach to different segments of the population and the targeting of social assistance. The most important task at this stage is to prevent a sharp stratification of society into excessively rich and excessively poor.

Beginning of the 1994, the system of social assistance in the republic increasingly acquires features characteristic of similar systems in countries with a market economy, the very concept of poverty and the methods of its quantitative measurement are changing, the sources of financing of social assistance and social insurance are more clearly delineated, group of beneficiaries.

Meanwhile social assistance is aimed at supporting the most vulnerable segments of the population, that is, those who for objective reasons are not able to earn their livelihood themselves (children, the elderly, disabled and other persons not engaged in production for reasons beyond their control), then the need for it is determined, first of all, by the demographic situation in the republic, by the level of income of the population and by the nature of their distribution, established by the standards of consumption, as well as by national traditions and historical individuals life.

In order to provide social assistance to needy families, orphans, invalids, veterans of war and labor in September 1992, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a presidential charity fund "Mahalla", whose funds were created from revenues from the state budget, as well as charitable contributions enterprises, organizations and individuals.

Results

In the early stages of Uzbekistan's independent development, the issues of maintaining security, ensuring stability, and what should be the main focus of development along the chosen path of development were of strategic importance. After

all, only if stability and geographical-political balance were preserved in the country, there was a chance for vigorous and stable development in the whole region, to become a worthy partner in the world community.

Uzbekistan supported the principle that "security is a continuous state" in the fight against existing threats. In addition to the political threats explored in this article, ethnic, regional, local conflicts, environmental and nuclear security issues were growing for the country at that time. Threats to the security of our country, nation, society, and every citizen, and threats to renewal and development were understood and analyzed, and the need to respond to them only through mutual cooperation was justified. In such a situation, the following tasks were implemented as ways to strengthen stability and guarantees of development in the country: 1. Restoration of spiritual values and awareness of national identity; 2. Formation of statehood and strengthening of defense capabilities; 3. Formation of democratic institutions and foundations of civil society; 4. Settlement of market relations and formation of the class of owners; 5. Strong social policy and increase in social activity of the population; 6. Geographical strategic opportunities and natural raw materials resources; 7. Human potential, social and production infrastructure; 8. Extensive changes; 9. Cooperation with the world community [3].

Discussion

The path of development chosen by Uzbekistan, the problems of the transition period and the analysis of reforms on the way to sustainable development researched in the works of I.A. Karimov. In particular, the work "Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development" analyzes the place, position and future prospects of the country in the process of complex changes in the world and draws important conclusions. In this work, the need to implement reforms in order to achieve security, stability, steady development of the country and, on this basis, to ensure the well-being and decent living of our people, to take their place in the world community, the main content of

achieving the independence and sovereignty of the state, the freedom and equality of the people, the main content it was based on the purpose.

I.A. Karimov identified the main priorities for further modernization of the country in, adopted on November 12, 2010 "Concepts of further deepening democratic reforms and the formation of civil society in the country": democratization of state power and administration, reform of the judicial and legal system, reform of the information sphere and ensuring freedom of speech and information, ensuring freedom of choice and development of electoral legislation, the formation and development of civil society institutions, further deepening market reforms and liberalizing the economy[4]. It has opened a new stage in the development of Uzbekistan.

Today, the issues of ensuring the modernization of the country and achieving development are included in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 [5].

The issues of transitional problems and principles of sustainable development were also studied in the works of local scientists A. Kadirov [6], A. Utamurodov [7], B. Amonov [8], G. Tulenova [9], Sh. Madaeva [10].

In the article, an attempt was made to reflect on some issues related to some threats to Uzbekistan's security during the transition period and the nature of the reforms in society and state building based on the strategy and principles used in the fight against them.

Conclusions

The system of social assistance to low-income families in Uzbekistan today represents a successful experience in adapting modern managerial technologies to the mentality of the people, attracting the attention of representatives of many countries and international organizations.

In this way, the philosophy of reforms in the political sphere, in essence, is a reflection of a common, integrated vision of the forthcoming changes, goals and objectives in all spheres of social relations. For political modernization, it was also

necessary to have appropriate organizational, legal and socio-economic conditions. Considering the importance of restoring confidence in the authorities and improving the social status of people, after the deep economic recession and the collapse of the USSR, the new government required the formation of social optimism, respect for the spirit and the letter of the law, and the strengthening of the welfare of the masses.

The country, in the person of its political leadership, proclaimed the de-idealization of state institutions. These processes included the construction of a special social model that takes into account and stimulates a variety of opinions, genuine political pluralism, and respect for someone else's point of view.

The peculiarity of political modernization in Uzbekistan was also in the justification and implementation of new principles stemming from the existence of a kind of centuries-old philosophy, political culture, national mentality and the demographic situation of the country.

Among these principles is the movement from the simple to the complex, staged and systematic. Such conceptual approaches allowed avoiding social cataclysms and social upheavals, mitigating the consequences of market transformation and democratic renewal.

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